

1 **Immune activation status in the blood in HIV-1 infection.**

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6 We measured total transcription by microarray in the whole blood in healthy males and in HIV-1+ males for
7 discovery of activation markers associated with HIV-1 infection in vivo. We demonstrate activation of
8 *CD160* in the blood during HIV-1 infection. The cell death and exhaustion receptor *PDCD1* was
9 concomitantly induced in active infection. Humans with HIV-1 infection produced large amounts of *CCL5*
10 and *CCL4L1*. T-cell exhaustion was affected with activation of both *TIGIT* and *LAG3* and induction of
11 *EOMES* and *THEMIS*. Humans with HIV-1 infection activated *Ifi27* as well as the G-protein receptors
12 *Gpr18* and *Gpr89b*.

13 Citations

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